

POLYMER-GRAFTED SILICA NANOPARTICLES FOR IMPROVING MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF COATINGS AND RESINS

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SUMMARY

Polymer-grafted core/shell particles can be synthesized as dispersions in common solvents. Abrasion tests show that the scratch resistance clear-coats can be significantly increased. The developed technology platform is also suitable to yield epoxy-polymer modified nanoparticles which are compatible with common EP construction resins. Some preliminary investigations show a significant improvement in the mechanical properties.

Keywords: Nanocomposite, Nanoparticles, core/shell, Scratch resistance

The demands are high, being placed on coatings today concerning mechanical toughness. Scratches in the surface are a well-known problem which is disturbing especially for glossy and dark surfaces.

For a long time now, inorganic nanoparticles have been discussed as a way to increase the scratch resistance of coatings. However, at present the realization is often limited because inorganic materials are foreign matter to the organic resin and combining these two worlds on a nanometer level is a challenging task. Often compatibility problems occur during processing, such as agglomeration, haze and increased viscosity, limiting the scope of applicability. The reason for this is mainly the insufficient stabilization of the hydrophilic nanoparticles in the hydrophobic environment of a coating system.

The surfaces of nanoparticles usually show a high surface energy and bear hydroxyl groups which render them hydrophilic. In an unpolar environment like a solvent or a resin the nanoparticles tend to reduce the interface exposed to the unpolar matrix by agglomeration. Once the inorganic surfaces come in contact with each other, condensation reactions of the hydroxyl groups take place, making the process almost irreversible.

Figure 1: Schematic sketch of polymer-grafted core/shell nanoparticles. The reactive group bearing polymer resin shell is covalently bound to the SiO₂ core.

Starting from dispersions like e.g. colloidal silica sol, these particles are synthesized as transparent dispersions in common solvents like butylacetate or hydrocarbons using a grafting-from polymerisation process. Once the polymer shell is attached, the nanoparticle dispersion can be handled like a solution of an organic resin. The nanoparticle dispersion can be dried to a powder and redispersed in typical solvents down to primary particle size simply with a spatula without the need of external dispersion aids. In practice, the solid content can be varied between 1-80%.

Figure 2: TEM pictures of a cured conventional 2K PU clear-coat containing 40 weight% core/shell particles. The resin shell ensures very good dispersion behaviour of the nanoparticles without the need for high shear forces. The high content is for demonstration purposes only.

The polymer shell can be built up from commonly available monomers, thus allowing enough flexibility to adapt the particle to the target resin. In general, the coating producer has the freedom to use this material as an additive solution to add scratch resistance “drop by drop” without major changes to his known coating system.

To investigate the effect of the core/shell nanoparticles on the scratch resistance of solvent based 2K PU clear-coats, the binder resin was partly replaced by the C–OH functional core/shell particles to maintain a constant NCO:OH ratio.

As a widely accepted scratch resistance test method, the Crockmeter test (9 μm 3M wet-or-dry abrasive paper; 9 N load; 10 double strokes) was used and the gloss was measured before and after the test at a 20° angle.

Conventional 2K PU clear-coats were investigated. As an example, an automotive refinish clear-coat cured at 60 °C is shown in figure 3.

Figure 3: Gloss measurement of a 2K PU Refinish coating cured at 60 °C/30 min with varying level of core/shell nanoparticles (weight% based on non-volatile components). Crockmeter test 9 μm 3M wet or dry sanding paper with 10 double strokes at 9 N load.

It can be seen clearly, that already the addition of 2.5% nanoparticles shows a significant effect. The coatings maintain a higher gloss immediately after the scratching and improve further after the reflow cycle (2 h at 80 °C) which simulates the parking of the vehicle in the sun at elevated temperatures for some hours. Allowing the material to flow at elevated temperatures is an indication that the coating material does not become brittle due to the addition of the nanoparticles.

It is worthwhile noting that the initial gloss of the coatings is not affected by the incorporation of the nanoparticles which indicates a good compatibility.

The EDX scan of the Si signal across a coatings cross section shows the homogenous dispersion of the nanoparticles throughout a coating (Bayer solvent based DD 2K-PU OEM clearcoat; published recipe).

Figure 4: EDX Si signal mapping of the cross section of a 2K PU automotive OEM coating containing 10 weight% core/shell nanoparticles based on non-volatile components.

Figure 5: 2K PU automotive OEM clear-coat without (left) and with 5 % core/shell nanoparticles (right) after crockmeter test with 9 μm abrasive paper. Curing temperature: 130 °C; car shape models based on carbon black coloured polycarbonate.

Currently, further work is concentrated on gathering more knowledge about structure-property relationships and on the adaption of the core/shell nanoparticles to waterborne, UV-curing and epoxy nanocomposite systems.

Core/Shell Nanoparticle modified Epoxy resins

Since polymer chemistry allows the introduction of the epoxy group into the polymer shell, it becomes possible to introduce core/shell nanoparticles as crosslinking nano-additives also in epoxy resins.

Nanoparticles already have been investigated as an additive to CFC's in order to increase the fracture toughness. However the existing problems with viscosity increase and compatibility issues are not yet solved.

Conventional epoxy resins like Bisphenol-A-diglycidylether and Tetraglycidyl-4,4'-methylenebisbenzenamine were mixed with varying amounts of the core/shell nanoparticles and cured with methyltetrahydrophthalic anhydride.

Figure 6: Electron microscopy image of cured Tetraglycidyl 4,4' methylenbisbenzenamine epoxy resin containing 9 vol% epoxy-modified core/shell particles.

Figure 6 shows the homogenous distribution of the particles in the cured resin without agglomerates. This is the precondition for a good penetration of the carbon fibers and a reinforcement effect in a CFC.

T_g and storage modulus were measured with DMA for the neat resin and different core/shell polymer compositions. Table 1 shows some results for 9 vol% nanoparticle content.

Table 1. T_g and storage modulus of Tetraglycidyl 4,4' methylenbisbenzenamine (MY721) containing 9 vol% epoxy-modified core/shell particles with different polymer chemistry.

Sample Code	$T_g(^{\circ}C)$	$E'@30^{\circ}C$ (GPa)	$E'@175^{\circ}C$ (GPa)	$E'@250^{\circ}C$ (MPa)
MY721	235.6	2.77	1.89	104.6
FD187.3	238.5	2.92	1.98	148.9
FD187.5	239.4	2.80	1.85	155.9
FD187.6	240	2.94	2.0	168.3

T_g and storage modulus are significantly increased by most core/shell compositions.

The fracture toughness was measured for a Bisphenol-A-diglycidylether cured resin at increasing amounts of SiO₂ core/shell nanoparticles.

Figure 7: Fracture toughness of a Bisphenol-A-diglycidylether at increasing amounts of SiO₂ core/shell nanoparticles.

Figure 7 shows, that K_{IC} could be significantly improved even at addition of small amounts of nanoparticles. The fracture surface was investigated with SEM and shows a possible mechanism for the improved fracture toughness. It seems probable that when a crack propagates through the material and hits a nanoparticle, the crack is split up and branches out, thus maximising the energy necessary for breaking.

Figure 8: SEM images of the crack propagation in the neat resin and nanoparticle-filled resin.

These first investigations show a promising potential of the core/shell nanoparticles in the field of epoxy matrix reinforcement for CFC's. Further tests are necessary to optimize the core/shell particles to the full requirement profile of carbon fiber composites.